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EVALUATION OF A PSYCHOSOCIAL INTERVENTION TO ENHANCE RESILIENCE AND DECREASE PSYCHOLOGICAL DISTRESS IN UNACCOMPANIED ASYLUM-SEEKING MINORS

Relevance of research: This research contributes to understanding of vulnerability and resilience among unaccompanied asylum-seeking minors (UAMs) in forced migration to Europe and presents the findings of a pilot group intervention to enhance resilience and decrease psychological distress in UAMs.

Purpose of research: The purpose of the research was to evaluate the effectiveness of a group-based psychosocial intervention (Taking Part, TP) to enhance resilience and decrease psychological distress in UAMs following resettlement in the UK. An increasing number of UAMs have been forced to migrate alone to seek asylum in UK and are known to experience psychological distress. Many of them are considered to need individual clinic-based therapy; however, helping them to build resilience could offset this need.

Methods: A pragmatic randomised controlled trial was employed to evaluate the effectiveness of the TP psychosocial intervention. The participants (n=30), aged 15 to 17 years, were randomly assigned to one of the two conditions: experimental (n=15) and wait-list control (n=15) groups. The experimental group received 14 hours of TP intervention to enhance resilience-building skills, while the wait-list control group received standard support services provided by a refugee agency. Measures of resilience and psychological distress were administered pre- and post-intervention to both groups. Data analyses comprised of a combination of descriptive and inferential statistics, and intervention fidelity outcomes.

Results: Analyses indicated that the experimental group had significantly higher resilience scores (i.e., increases in optimistic thinking, reduction in pessimistic thinking) and lower scores in psychological distress (i.e., reduction in depressive symptoms) post-intervention than did the wait-list control group.

Conclusions: These findings suggest that psychosocial intervention may be useful to enhance resilience and decrease psychological distress in UAMs.

Keywords: unaccompanied; asylum-seeking minors; resilience; psychological distress.